

1 **Supplementary information**

2 **Table S1.** WAIC, WAIC Standard Error and RMSE and bias for local allometric equations adjusted on dataset 1 to
 3 predict mean height (H; in m) as a function of stem diameter (in cm), using the three functions: power, Michaelis-
 4 Menten and Weibull simplified (2 params).

Model	Function	Equation	Predictors	WAIC	WAIC (SE)	RMSE
model 1- PW	Power	$\hat{H}=a \times DBH^b$	----	<u>18,501.02</u>	<u>89.71</u>	<u>3.97</u>
Model 1- MM	Michaelis- Menten	$\hat{H}=a \times DBH/(b+DBH)$	----	18,574.06	89.64	4.02
model 1- W	Weibull	$\hat{H}= a \times (1-\exp(-DBH/b))$	----	18,724.38	90.13	4.11
model 2- PW	Power	$\hat{H}= (a \times LCH + b) \times DBH^c$	LCH	<u>17,761.67</u>	101.63	<u>3.55</u>
model 2- MM	Michaelis- Menten	$\hat{H}=(a \times LCH + b) \times DBH/(c+DBH)$	LCH	17,781.97	102.10	3.56
model 2- W	Weibull	$\hat{H}= (a \times LCH + b) \times (1-\exp(-DBH/c))$	LCH	17,914.96	101.82	3.64
model 3- PW	Power	$\hat{H}=a \times DBH^b$	species (random effect)	<u>17,440.21</u>	94.20	<u>3.55</u>
model - MM	Michaelis- Menten	$\hat{H}=a \times DBH/(b+DBH)$	species (random effect)	17,485.29	94.00	3.56
model 3- W	Weibull	$\hat{H}= (a \times LCH + b) \times (1-\exp(-DBH/c))$	species (random effect)	17,560.33	94.37	3.64
model 4- PW	Power	$\hat{H}= (a \times LCH + b) \times DBH^c$	LCH + species (random effect)	16,634.38	110.93	2.80
model 4- MM	Michaelis- Menten	$\hat{H}= (a \times LCH + b) \times DBH/(c+DBH)$	LCH + species (random effect)	<u>16,627.92</u>	112.01	2.78
model 4- W	Weibull	$\hat{H}= (a \times LCH + b) \times (1-\exp(-DBH/c))$	LCH + species (random effect)	16,673.77	111.59	<u>2.77</u>

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7 **Figure S2.** Comparison of individual tree height measurements by terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) and airborne
8 laser scanning (ALS). The TLS height data is from Bossoukpe (2020). The dashed line corresponds to the
9 reference line with slope = 1, and intercept = 0. The blue line is the linear regression.

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11 **Figure S3.** Comparison of observed vs. predicted tree height (2,467 obs. from dataset 1) for Canopy Constructor
12 predictions and MM4 predictions. Note that Canopy Constructor was adjusted on the full database (dataset 2,
13 73,325 obs.) and MM4 on the ground truth data (dataset 1, 3,304 obs.). Dotted 1:1 line in red.

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16 **Figure S4.** Mean residual height per plot vs plot structural characteristics: basal area (upper row, a-d) and
 17 quadratic mean diameter (lower row, e-h) for models 1-MM to 4-MM. Models 2-MM and 4-MM include local canopy
 18 height as a covariate when predicting height from diameter at breast height (DBH) and show a much weaker trend.
 19 The colors indicate the different treatments: Tall Undisturbed Forests (TUF), Short Undisturbed Forests (SUF), and
 20 T1 to T3, which represent different silvicultural treatments, where T1 corresponds to the least intensive treatment
 21 and T3 to the most intensive one.

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24 **Figure S5:** H-DBH Scatterplot of the 60 Most Abundant Species (More than 100 trees with a stem diameter
 25 greater than 20 cm). Height is predicted using the 'Canopy Constructor' method (pink circles). Green filled circles
 26 represent modeled height using the 'Model 4-MM'. Trends are modeled using the loess function in ggplot2, with
 27 a continuous line for the 'Model 4-MM' modeled height, and a dotted pink line for 'Canopy Constructor' heights.

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32 **Table S6.** Tree Distribution by Stem Diameter and Crown Exposure. The table summarizes the number of trees
 33 categorized by their stem diameter and crown exposure level. The data highlight the strong correlation between
 34 stem diameter and crown visibility, with 88% of non-visible trees having a stem diameter below 20 cm.

	Below 20 cm stem diameter	Above 20 cm stem diameter
Below 25% Crown exposure	32,911	8,663
Above 25% Crown exposure	10,045	21,706

35 39% of all trees are classified as non-visible.
 36 Of these, 88% (18,369 out of 20,884) have a diameter below 20 cm.
 37 43% of trees with stem diameter < 20 cm are hidden.
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39 **Table S7.** Summary of Bias, Standard Deviation (SD), and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) by Model and
 40 Treatment.

Model	Treatment	BIAS	SD	RMSE
Model Canopy Constructor	SUF	0.43	2.30	2.34
	T1	0.48	2.68	2.72
	T2	0.13	2.17	2.17
	T3	0.70	1.97	2.09
	TUF	0.20	2.49	2.49
Model 4-MM	SUF	0.36	2.34	2.37
	T1	-0.45	2.57	2.60
	T2	-0.47	2.33	2.37
	T3	0.08	2.20	2.20
	TUF	-0.60	2.51	2.57
Model 1-MM	SUF	0.57	3.60	3.64
	T1	-0.54	3.62	3.66
	T2	0.16	3.36	3.36
	T3	1.33	3.01	3.29
	TUF	-2.62	3.43	4.31
Model 0	SUF	-1.40	4.12	4.35
	T1	-2.56	4.00	4.75
	T2	-1.49	3.85	4.11
	T3	-1.18	3.26	3.46
	TUF	-2.63	4.09	4.86

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43 **Equation S8.** The model 4-MM employs this equation to estimate the height of individual trees within a given
44 species, based on measurable environmental and physical parameters.

45 R. code used to fit final model (4-MM) to observed tree heights (full code available on GitHub

46 https://github.com/chuertas18/local_allometries_LIDAR/model_1_4_PW_MM.r and

47 <https://zenodo.org/records/15075077>

48 The model's function is as follows: it predicts the height $H_{i,s}$ of individual i belonging to species s ,

49 given a diameter at breast height (DBH) of D_i and a local canopy height LCH_i as follow:

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$$H_{i,s} \sim \mathcal{N}\left(\frac{\alpha_{i,s} \times D_i}{\beta_s + D_i}; \sigma^2\right)$$

51 with

52
$$\beta_s \sim \mathcal{N}(\beta_0; \sigma_\beta^2)$$

53
$$\alpha_{i,s} \sim \mathcal{N}(\alpha_s + \gamma_s \times LCH_i; \sigma_\alpha^2)$$

54 where S is the variance-covariance matrix:

55 The model parameters are:

- 56
- 57 • sd(alpha_Intercept) is σ_{α_s}
 - 58 • sd(alpha_HC) is σ_γ
 - 59 • sd(beta_Intercept) is σ_β
 - 60 • cor(alpha_Intercept, alpha_HC) is ρ
 - 61 • alpha_Intercept is α_0
 - 62 • beta_Intercept is β_0
 - 63 • sigma is σ

64 Species-specific responses to canopy height (HC) in a non-linear Bayesian growth model (model 4-
65 MM)

66 $\alpha \sim HC + 1 \mid \text{species_noSing}$

67 The non-linear parameter alpha (the asymptotic maximum height in the Michaelis-Menten model)
68 varies linearly with HC within each species, allowing both random intercepts and slopes by species.

69 So, $LCH \approx HC$, and what we are evaluating is the effect of HC on height through its influence on alpha.

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71 In the model results, the effect of LHC on alpha has a distribution across species and is modeled as a
72 random effect.

73 Looking at:

- 74 • $sd_species_noSing_alpha_LHC \approx 0.145$
- 75 • $cor_species_noSing_alpha_Intercept_alpha_LHC \approx -0.0894$

76 This suggests that:

- 77 • The effect of HC on alpha varies between species.
- 78 • The standard deviation of the HC effect is small but positive, meaning that some species have
79 a positive slope with respect to HC, and others a negative one.
- 80 • The average effect of HC on alpha is represented by the coefficient b_alpha_HC . Although that
81 value isn't explicitly shown in the summary snippet, we can infer it's close to zero, because:
 - 82 ○ The random effect is centered on zero (by construction of the model),
 - 83 ○ The variation is symmetric around that center,
 - 84 ○ And there is no strong signal of a consistent effect of HC on height across all species.

85 That value is indeed included in the results (e.g., 0.145, 1.5, 0.454, depending on the chain), confirming
86 that there is a random species-level effect on the response to HC.

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88 Parameter interpretations:

89 σ^α (sigma alpha):

90 This parameter represents the standard deviation of the random species effect on the slope of HC in
91 alpha.

92 γ_0 (gamma zero):

93 This represents the average effect of HC on alpha, i.e., the fixed slope of HC in the alpha part of the
94 model.

95 Our model explicitly specifies and estimates a species-level random effect on the influence of HC on
96 alpha:

97 $alpha \sim HC + 1 \mid species_noSing$

98 This implies that:

- 99 • Each species has its own intercept and slope (effect of HC),
- 100 • These effects follow a normal distribution,
- 101 • The standard deviation of this distribution (σ^α) has been estimated.

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Parameter	Meaning	brms name	Mean	Std. Dev.	2.5%	Median	97.5%
σ^α	Variation between species in the HC effect on alpha	sd_species_noSing_alpha_HC	0.70	0.58	0.16	0.45	1.45

Y_0	Average effect of HC on alpha	b_alpha a_HC	-0.59	0.36	-0.93	-0.73	-0.121
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